

CONSOLIDATION OF MECHANICALLY MILLED AL-MWCNT NANO-COMPOSITE BY THE CONVENTIONAL POWDER METALLURGY PROCESSING

Hendrik, K. H. Han*

School of Materials Science and Engineering, Yeungnam University, Gyeongsan, Gyeongbuk, Korea

* Corresponding author (khhan@ynu.ac.kr)

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1 Introduction

Because of their excellent mechanical and thermal properties, the multi-wall carbon nano-tube (MWCNT) has been considered as a promising reinforcing material for light weight aluminum and its alloys.[1-2] In the preparation of Al-MWCNT nano composites, the uniform dispersion of MWCNT in the aluminum matrix has been a big concern since they tend to cluster themselves owing to van der Waals interactions between them. From the previous researches, it is now known that the combined use of sonication in a proper liquid media and high energy ball milling is most effective for that purpose. [3-5]

However, the mechanically milled powders possess rather poor sinterability and, on sintering at higher temperatures for densification, the unstable aluminum carbide, Al_4C_3 , is prone to form due to the reaction between aluminum and MWCNT. [6] This carbide phase, when exposed to the moisture, decomposes into aluminum hydroxide with the evolution of methane [7], resulting in the degradation of carbide-containing aluminum matrix composites. [8] Hence, it is desired to avoid its formation during consolidation processing.

Many researchers employed lower temperature processing below $600^\circ C$, but in order to enhance densification of Al-MWCNT nano-composite powders, a combined processing of pre-sintering followed by severe working of hot extrusion at high reduction ratio and, multi-pass hot rolling, etc. is utilized.[9-12] However, the severe hot deformation for densification limits the final form of sinter products to a simple shape of extruded or rolled forms having a highly directional anisotropy in mechanical properties. Recently, the use of spark

plasma sintering (SPS) to obtain a dense part has also been attempted. [11-12]

This study was undertaken to investigate the applicability of conventional powder metallurgy process, i.e., cold compaction and pressureless sintering, to the production of Al-MWCNT nano-composite parts in near net shape.

2 Experimental Procedures

2.1 Preparation of Nano-composite Powders

99.5wt.% pure aluminum powders with an average size of about $5\mu m$ (MEP105, the product of MEURA Metall Pulvergesellschaft GmbH, Austria) and MWCNT grown by CVD method and having a dimension of 10-15nm in diameter and 10-20 μm in length (CM-95, the product of Hanwha Nanotech,

Fig. 1. SEM images of starting materials, Al powder (a) and MWCNT (b), and milled powders, (c) and (d); inset in (d) shows the entangled clusters (indicated by the arrows) in milled powders.

Korea) were used as starting materials. In order to disperse MWCNTs uniformly over Al powders we utilized the sonication in ethanol for 30min and mechanical milling. To prevent excessive cold welding between Al powders during mechanical milling, we added 0.5wt.% polyethylene wax (Acumist B-12, the product of Honeywell corp., USA) and 3cc ethanol as a process controlling agent. Also 1%Mg was added to improve sinterability of milled powders. Mechanical milling was performed using a planetary mill (Pulverisette 5, FRITSCH, Germany) at 200 rpm for 2hrs in Ar atmosphere. Cemented carbide 10mm ϕ balls were charged at the ball-to-powder ratio of 10:1 into the cemented carbide-line jars.

2.2 Consolidation of Nano-composite Powders

Using the mold and punches made of cemented carbide, the powder mixture was compacted into discs with a dimension of 10mm ϕ in diameter and 8mm in height. The compaction pressure was varied from 200MPa to 1GPa. The green compacts were dewaxed at 450 $^{\circ}$ C for 30min and sintered at 650 $^{\circ}$ C for 2hrs in different atmospheres of vacuum, argon, or nitrogen. The gas flow rate was 0.2l/min. The vacuum level for vacuum sintering was about 10 $^{-2}$ torr.

2.3 Materials Characterizations

The density of green compact and sinter was determined by the water displacement method as

Fig. 2. Relative density of green compact as a function of applied pressure. For comparison, the data for as-atomized pure Al are included.

described in MPIF standard 42. The phase analysis of sintered Al-MWCNT samples was done by the x-ray diffraction and the metallographic observation. The x-ray diffraction was done using a diffractometer equipped with a diffracted beam crystal monochromator and Cu-K $_{\alpha}$ radiation. The microstructure observation was made in optical microscope. The Raman spectroscopy (T64000, Horiba Jobin Yvon, France) was performed with the laser wavelength of 514nm and exposure time was 5s.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Consolidation

Fig. 1 shows the SEM images of starting materials of aluminum powders (a) and MWCNTs (b) and the morphology(c) and dispersion (d) of MWCNT in the milled powders. In Fig. 1(c), Al-MWCNT flattened and fractured powders are seen along with some large particles experienced cold welding. Fig. 1(d) reveals MWCNTs partly embedded in the powders. Also, some large entangled clusters of MWCNT in milled powders are seen in the inset of Fig. 1(d).

The compressibility of the milled powders was examined first. For comparison, the same tests were made for atomized Al powders. As shown in Fig. 2, the milled powders showed poor compressibility. Under the same compaction pressure the relative density for the milled powders was about 8% lower than that for atomized Al powders. Even above 800MPa, the relative density of milled powder compact did not reach 90%, while it was about 95% for pure Al powders. For such inferior compressibility of the milled powders, among others, the presence of individual MWCNTs and non-dispersed entangled MWCNT clusters on the surface of the milled powders would be mainly responsible. Together with this, possible uptake of oxygen during milling and work hardened milled powders would be another factors for inferior compressibility.

2 X-ray observation

Fig. 3 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns obtained from the Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg samples after sintering at 650 $^{\circ}$ C for 2hrs in different atmospheres; (A) vacuum, (B) Ar and (C) N $_2$. Each set of patterns shows the changes in X-ray diffraction patterns as a function of compaction pressure or green density of compacts. First of all, we note that in all three

sintering atmospheres, the formation of additional phase has occurred. Sintering in vacuum and Ar

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction patterns of Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg after sintering at 650°C in (A) vacuum, (B) Ar and (C) N₂; (a) 200MPa, (b) 400MPa, (c) 800MPa and (d) 1GPa, respectively.

accompanied the formation of Al₄C₃, and, probably due to poor vacuum condition, the existence of magnesium spinel, MgAl₂O₄ was further detected. In contrast, sintering in nitrogen did not produce aluminum carbide (Fig. 3(C)). Instead, AlN in a traceable amount in X-ray pattern appeared.

The observation of the formation of aluminum carbide in the samples sintered in Ar and in vacuum can be compared with the result of our separate experiment made for non-milled, blended powder molded compact. For this compact, no appreciable amount of aluminum carbide was observed in X-ray diffraction pattern after sintering in Ar under the same sintering schedule. This comparative study points that the formation of aluminum carbide in milled powder samples would be caused by activation for the reaction between Al and MWCNT due to milling, due to physical damage in MWCNT of local amorphization on its surfaces, especially near or at its ends. Recent transmission electron microscopy study suggested that such defects at opening of MWCNT play important role for the formation of aluminum carbide phase by acting as preferential sites for its nucleation.[13]

The disordering in MWCNT due to local amorphization in the milled powders can be monitored by comparing the intensities of the two Raman peaks at 1580cm⁻¹ and 1350cm⁻¹, known as G (graphitic) band and D (disorder) band; the former characterizes the stretching mode of the C-C bond in the graphite plane and the latter represents the disordered radial mode due to finite domain size.[12-13] As shown in Fig. 4, a decrease of the intensity ratio of D band to G band, I_D/I_G of MWCNT after milling is noted, which can be regarded a measure of their degradation. The I_D/I_G ratio in raw MWCNT and milled powder were 0.86 and 1.04, respectively. Also, the shift of G band as appreciated in Fig. 4 is caused by the residual compressive residual stress in MWCNT. [14-15]

The absence of aluminum carbide peaks in the sinter produced in nitrogen (Fig. 3(C)) is quite interesting. This differs from the expectation that intimate contact between aluminum and MWCNT in milled powders would be sufficient to activate the carbide formation at elevated temperatures since it is a thermodynamically favorable reaction.[16]

The formation of AlN in Al-based powder compacts in N₂ occurs via direct reaction between Al powder and nitrogen gas and it is a spontaneous and

Fig. 4. Raman spectra at 514nm excitation, taken from the milled powder and its sinter; for comparison, the result for raw MWCNT is included.

exothermic process. The extent of AlN formation in the compact depends on the amount of open channels (pores) that provide fast paths for transportation of nitrogen into the inside of it. Hence, the lower green density resulted in higher amounts of AlN. The formation AlN on the surface of milled

powders, especially in loosely compacted powders, however, hinder the atomic transfer between adjacent powders in contact and leads to poor densification.[17] Higher green density provides less open channels both in size and population, so that nitride formation becomes less pronounced and negligible eventually. As is seen in Fig. 3(C), the intensities of AlN peaks decreased with increasing compaction pressure.

As described above, this result, obviously, showed that the atmosphere used in sintering can play a crucial role in the suppression of Al₄C₃ carbide formation in milled Al-MWCNT powder compacts. The free energy for the formation of both Al₄C₃ and AlN compounds is negative but it is far more negative for AlN. [17] We note that most MWCNTs, either individuals or entangled clusters, are dispersed on the surface of milled powders and that nitride formation occurs preferentially at those boundary regions where nitrogen can easily diffuse into. Hence, regarding the suppression of carbide formation, a possible scenario can be such that N₂ molecules (or N atoms) would contaminate the nucleation sites for Al₄C₃, through some interaction with MWCNT. In order to check this hypothesis and

Fig. 5. Optical microstructures of Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg nano-composites after sintering at 650°C for 2hrs in N₂; the compaction pressure was (a) 200MPa, (b) 400MPa, (c) 800MPa and (d) 1GPa,

to provide clear understanding of this phenomenon, more detailed and analytic experiments are required utilizing transmission and analytic electron microscopy.

Also, it is to be noted in Fig. 3 that the diffracted intensities of the aluminum carbide in the nano-composites sintered in vacuum and Ar do not show appreciable changes with the increase of compaction pressure. This is in contrast to the reduction of AlN intensities with the compaction pressure observed for samples sintered in N₂.

3.3 Microstructure and densification

Fig. 5 is the optical macrostructures of Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg nano-composites sintered in N₂ at 650°C for 2hrs. The four optical microstructures were taken from the sintered samples prepared under different compaction pressure. The sinters contained fine microstructure of small platelet-shaped grains with an aspect ratio as high as about 5:1. The anisotropic grain shape is considered to originate from the deformed shape of the milled powders. For other samples sintered in vacuum and Ar, similar grain structure was observed.

In Fig. 5, the presence of small voids appearing as dark spots is noticed in the matrix. For sample compacted at lower pressure, their population and size of small voids were increased.

We note that the distribution of small voids in the matrix is fairly uniform. More specifically they exist along the boundaries of grains, where the population of individual MWCNTs and their untangled clusters is assumed high. This suggests, along with the fact that the wetting between Al and MWCNT is rather poor [18], that the void formation in the sinter would be affected by such non-uniform distribution of MWCNT and their clusters. Hence it is reasoned that the population and size of voids in the sinter can be related to the entangled MWCNT clusters existing at the boundaries between milled powders. That is, increasing compaction pressure will increase the extent of plastic deformation of milled powders, by shearing and stretching, to promote untangling agglomerated MWCNT clusters. The entangled MWCNT clusters still existing in the compact will adversely affect the densification during sintering, leaving small voids associated with those clusters. In this way, the population and size of MWCNT clusters will decrease, thereby resulting a reduction in the void population and size after sintering. Of

Fig. 6. Density of sinters of Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg produced under different atmospheres and relative green densities.

course, higher compaction pressure produces more effective breaking-up of surface oxide in milled powders, and provides more intimate mechanical interlocking between the powders to enhance sintering. Yet, the peculiar appearance and distribution of small voids favor their relevance to the MWCNT clusters on the surface of milled powders.

The Raman spectrum taken from the sinter (Fig. 4) ensured the retention of MWCNTs in aluminum matrix after sintering. The intensity ratio of I_D/I_G, was further increased from 1.04 to 1.15 after sintering, and the G peak position was displaced a bit more, which might be caused by further disordering of MWCNTs during cooling from the sintering temperature, due to the difference in the thermal expansion of MWCNT and aluminum[19].

4. Conclusions

Using Al-2%MWCNT-1%Mg nano-composite powders prepared by the sonication and mechanical milling, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The milled nano-composite powders possess poor compressibility; to produce green compact of a relative density near 90% at least an applied pressure of 800MPa is necessary.
- Sintering of the green compacts at 650°C both in vacuum and Ar resulted in the formation of Al₄C₃. However, in N₂ atmosphere, the carbide phase was not appreciated; instead, small amounts of AlN compound were identified.

- In order to attain high densification via pressureless sintering, the compaction pressure must be high enough; in our milled powder it must be at least 800MPa. Sintering in N₂ at 650°C for 2hrs retained MWCNTs in the aluminum matrix.

- The conventional powder metallurgy can be used as a consolidation method of milled nano-composite powders into in near net shape provided that dense green compact with its density of 85% or higher is provided and N₂ is used as sintering atmosphere.

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